

A Study of Hydrogen Bonding in Isomeric Chalkones

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UV and IR spectra of isomeric nitrochalkones have been studied to ascertain the nature of isomerism. The bands corresponding to carbonyl, nitro, ethylenic, and hydroxyl groups indicate that the *trans*-isomer contains the intramolecular hydrogen bonding between the carbonyl and 2'-hydroxyl groups, whereas the *cis*-isomer is stabilised by the intramolecular hydrogen bonding between 3'-nitro and 2'-hydroxyl groups.

Szmant and Basso¹ discussed the UV spectra of chalkones by considering the whole molecule as one conjugated system. Black and Lutz² compared the UV spectra of isomeric chalkones with those of isomeric stilbenes. Limura³ correlated the nature of the band at 210-230m μ with that for mononuclear aromatic compounds. Recently Jurd⁴ summarised the literature on the UV spectra of flavonoid compounds; the spectra were correlated with the relative resonance contributions of benzoyl and cinnamoyl forms to the total resonance of the molecule. Molho⁵ studied infrared spectra of flavanones using LiF monochromator and discussed the nature of O—H band in the light of the nature of intramolecular interactions. Recently carbonyl and hydroxyl stretching and C—H out-of-plane bending modes were studied for a series of flavanones and flavones⁶ and the influence of the substituents was discussed.

In the present communication spectroscopic method has been followed to ascertain the nature of isomerism of 2'-hydroxy-3'-nitrochalkones.

EXPERIMENTAL

The samples were prepared in the laboratory⁷. The *trans*-isomers were purified by crystallisation from acetic acid and *cis*-isomers, from ethanol.

UV spectra were determined on a Beckman DU spectrophotometer using spectroscopically pure ethanol. IR spectra were determined on a Beckman IR 4 spectrophotometer using KBr, NaCl, and LiF monochromators. Owing to the low solubility of the nitrochalkones in CCl₄, the IR spectra were determined by KBr pellet technique, using *ca.* 0.5

1. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 4397.

2. *Ibid.*, 1953, 75, 5990.

3. *Nippon Kagaku Zasshi*, 1956, 77, 1846.

4. "Chemistry of Flavonoids", edited by T. A. Geissman, Pergamon Press, New York, 1962, p. 107.

5. "Heterocycles oxygen es internationaux, De. La Recherche, Santifique Layon", 1955, pp. 5-10.

6. Brigg and Colebook, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1962, 18, 939.

7. Naik, Ph. D. Thesis, Poona University 1958, G ore, Ph. D. Thesis, Poona University 1958,

mg. of sample in 500 mg. of potassium bromide. Spectra in the LiF region (1 to 3.8μ) were determined in CCl_4 , using 1 cm matched quartz cells. The results are summarised in Table I.

DISCUSSION

trans-2'-Hydroxychalcone shows $\gamma\text{C}=\text{O}$ band at 1660 cm^{-1} , whereas benzylideneacetophenone shows at 1675 cm^{-1} . The *cis*-isomers of 2'-hydroxy-3'-nitrochalcones show γCO band at $\sim 1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$, corresponding to free carbonyl frequency in aromatic compounds. *trans*-2'-Hydroxy-3'-nitrochalcones show the lowering in $\gamma\text{C}=\text{O}$ by $\sim 50\text{ cm}^{-1}$ as compared to the corresponding *cis*-isomer. *trans*-isomers show no absorption in free O—H stretching region, whereas the *cis*-isomers show a weak but characteristic broad band at $\sim 3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. It is a general observation that a chelated hydroxyl group⁸ does not show any absorption at 3600 cm^{-1} ; the band shifts to a lower frequency region and is generally broad, probably due to the close vibrational levels⁹. Intramolecular hydrogen bonding between carbonyl and hydroxyl groups shows lowering in $\gamma\text{C}=\text{O}$. Thus the $\gamma\text{C}=\text{O}$ and OH-stretching frequencies for isomeric chalcones can be explained if we consider that the *trans*-isomer contains chelated hydroxyl group (I) with keto group, whereas *cis*-isomers contain hydrogen bonding between the nitro and hydroxyl group (II).

I (*trans*)

II (*cis*)

From Table I it is clear that both the symmetric and asymmetric bands at 1520 cm^{-1} and 1350 cm^{-1} due to $-\text{NO}_2$ group show a red shift for the *cis*-isomer¹¹; the intensity of these bands is comparatively enhanced in the *cis*-isomer. These results show a higher polar character of $-\text{NO}_2$ group in *cis*-isomer due to the intramolecular hydrogen bonding between $-\text{OH}$ and $-\text{NO}_2$ groups.

According to literature¹², the $\text{CH}=\text{CH}$ deformation bands are well defined in *trans*-isomer at 980 cm^{-1} (out-of-plane deformation) and $1325\text{--}1315\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (in-plane deformation),

8. Rasmussen *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 1068.

9. Pimental and McClellan, "The Hydrogen Bond", Freeman and Company, London, 1960, pp. 103-111.

10. Martin, *Nature*, 1950, **166**, 474; Horgert and Kurth, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 1622.

11. Francoel, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 1265; Lothrop *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1951, **73**, 3581; Randle and Whiffen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4153.

12. Sheppard and Sutherland, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1949, **A196**, 105; Kilpatrick and Pitzer, *J. Res. Nat. Bur. Standards*, 1947, **38**, 191; Shupard and Simpson, *Quart. Rev.*, 1953, **6**, 1.

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TABLE I

	UV spectra (EtOH). $\lambda_{\max}$ (m μ).	Molar absorp. ($\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$).	Stretching vibration. (cm $^{-1}$)		NO $_2$ (cm $^{-1}$)	C-H=C-H (cm $^{-1}$) deformation.	γ -Ring deformation (cm $^{-1}$).	
			C=O.	O-H.				Asymm.
A. Chalkone.	<i>trans</i>	310 228	3.1 1.2	1675 (s)	..	980 (m)	1312 (m)	Not studied
B. 2'-Hydroxy.	"	344 316	1.1 2.0	1660 (s)	..	978 (m)	1312 (m)	568 (m)
C. 2'-Hydroxy-4'-methyl-4-methoxy.	"	363 244	2.3 1.1	1638 (s)		988 (m)	1312 (m)	562 (m)
D. 2'-Hydroxy-5'-methyl-4-methoxy.	"	367 243	4.2 3.0	1638 (s)	..	980 (m)	1307 (m)	562 (m)
E. 2'-Hydroxy-3'-nitro-5'-methyl.	<i>cis</i>	319	1.6	1708 (s)	3413 (w)	1520 (s)	1348 (s)	702 (m)
E'. Do	<i>trans</i>	327	1.0	1653 (s)	..	1529 (s)	1352 (s)	990 (m)
F. 2'-Hydroxy-3'-nitro-4,4'-dimethoxy.	<i>cis</i>	326 257	6.9 1.8	1665 (s)	3308 (w)	1565 (s)	1360 (s)	715 (m)
F'. Do	<i>trans</i>	360 236	4.9 3.2	1635 (s)	..	Broad (s)	Broad (s)	904 (m)
G. 2'-Hydroxy-3'-nitro-5'-methyl,3,4-dimethoxy.	<i>cis</i>	346 277 234	0.6 0.6 3.14	1665 (s)	3407 (w)	1529 (s)	1346 (s)	699 (m)
G'. Do	<i>trans</i>	363 251	2.0 1.0	1640 (s)	..	1560 (s)	1359 (s)	980 (m)
H. 2',4-Dihydroxy-3'-nitro-5'-methyl,3-methoxy.	<i>cis</i>	365 319 233	2.0 2.3 1.9	1650 (s)	3340 (w)	1531 (s)	1346 (s)	703 (m)
H'. Do	<i>trans</i>	397 237	4.6 1.7	1645 (s)	..	Broad (s)	1355 (s)	983 (m)
I. 2'-Hydroxy-3'-nitro-5'-methyl,4- α -benzoyloxy.	<i>cis</i>	384 257	1.8 2.0	1701 (s)	3404 (w)	1520 (s)	1343 (s)	697 (m)
I'. Do	<i>trans</i>	292 236	1.7 2.6	1645 (s)	..	1525 (s)	1359 (s)	980 (m)

whereas these bands are absent in *cis*-isomers. It is clear from Table I that the in-plane deformation band is of medium intensity and is well separated from the 1345 cm^{-1} band (due to nitro group present in all nitrochalkones). *cis*-Isomer shows a characteristic band with medium intensity at $698\text{-}703\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which is not present in *trans*-isomers.

The bands in the region $700\text{-}600\text{ cm}^{-1}$, observed for aromatic compounds, are assigned to in-plane bending (β ring) modes¹³ and ring-breathing modes; the bands due to out-of-plane (γ -ring) modes¹³⁻¹⁴ lie in the region $700\text{-}300\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The position of γ -ring vibrations is mainly influenced by the position of substituents. From the comparison of the IR spectra in KBr region of chalkones, it is observed that all chalkones show two characteristic bands in the range $490\text{-}50\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to out-of-plane bending modes (γ -ring modes). The position of these bands depends on the substitution on the rings A and B. The distance between the γ -ring frequencies decreases with the increase of mass of the nuclei. The *cis*-isomers show higher γ -ring vibrational frequencies as compared to the *trans*-isomers. In fact, we expect a lower energy for bonding in the case of *trans*-isomer due to the lower double bond character for ethylene group, as explained by the resonance form (V); in the *cis*-isomer resonance form (IV) plays important role, showing intramolecular hydrogen bonding between 3'-nitro and 2'-hydroxyl groups and therefore ethylene group will have higher double bond character.

The nature of isomerism, discussed on the basis of IR spectra, is confirmed by the study of UV spectra. The chalkones show two absorption bands due to charge transfer, one (V) in the region $300\text{-}400\text{ m}\mu$ and the other (IV) in the region $200\text{-}290\text{ m}\mu$. The nature of intramolecular hydrogen bonding will have an important effect on the contribution of different resonance forms. Intramolecular hydrogen bonding between the carbonyl and 2'-hydroxyl will be favoured by both the resonance forms, whereas the $-M$ effect of nitro group will oppose the structure (IV). It is clear from the spectra of E, F, G, H, and I that band (V) shows a blue shift but band (IV) shows a large red shift in *cis*-isomer as compared to a *trans*-one. *cis*-Isomer is stabilised by intramolecular hydrogen bonding

13. Katritzky, "Physical Methods in Heterocyclic Chemistry", Vol II, Academic Press, New York and London, 1963, p. 282.

14. Bell *et al.*, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1948, 192A, 498; Colce and Thompson, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1950, 46, 103.

between 3'-nitro and 2'-hydroxyl groups by favouring resonance form(IV) showing a red shift in band (IV) and a blue shift in band (V).

The following sterically unfavourable structure may contribute to the spectroscopic properties of chalkones. Structure(VI) will explain the low intensity band due to -OH stretching frequency, indicating weak intramolecular hydrogen bonding in the *cis*-isomer between -C=O and -OH groups; the lowering of -NO₂ frequency in *cis*-isomer, the observation of carbonyl frequency corresponding to free C=O group, and the nature of γ -ring frequencies cannot, however, be explained on the basis of (VI), thus favouring the conclusion of intramolecular hydrogen bonding between -NO₂ and -OH in the *cis*-isomer corresponding to (II).

The UV and IR studies thus show the difference in the nature of the intramolecular hydrogen bonding in isomeric chalkones; the intramolecular hydrogen bonding in *cis*-isomer favours the stability of *cis*-3'-nitro-2'-hydroxychalkones and which are therefore comparatively stable and can be easily prepared as compared to other *cis*-chalkones.

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